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KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS REGARDING RISK-FACTORS ASSOCIATE WITH COVID-19 AMONG URBAN POOR IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

COVID-19 has become a global pandemic as well as deadly disease. COVID-19 pandemic has brought vulnerability to the people especially among urban poor in Bangladesh. Lack of knowledge and awareness regarding COVID-19 has occurred miserable condition. The study explores the socio-demographic background of urban poor, the level of knowledge and the Awareness regarding risk-factors associated with COVID-19 among urban poor. This cross-sectional study was conducted in urban slum during the period from July, 2020 to July 30, 2020. Structured interview schedule executed in urban slum for collecting data among 269 respondents. The study was carried out in Kamrangichar slum of Dhaka city in Bangladesh. For investigating significant association between variables and analysis knowledge regarding among slum dwellers, frequency, chi-square and multinomial logistic regression has performed. According to survey, 67.3% of examined respondents heard about COVID-19, in verse, 13.0% of respondents have never heard about COVID-19. Unfortunately, only 38.7% respondents have heard about quarantine. Similarly, same result found knowledge regarding social distancing. For building knowledge and awareness regarding risk factors, respondents preferred local announcement more than radio television. Respondents also suggested for help of local health workers for creating awareness. They also stated that government active participation can prevent spreading disease from urban slums of Bangladesh

Keyword: *Knowledge, Risk-factors, Awareness, Urban poor,*

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Introduction

COVID-19 has become a global pandemic as well as deadly disease. Globally, as the report of WHO, 24 July 2020, there have been 15,257,287 confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 628,240 deaths, Still America, Europe and south-east Asia are located as the most susceptible places of transmission of this diseases. It impacts highly on socio-economic, demographic and political structure of the society. South-Asian countries like Bangladesh, Pakistan, India etc are highly susceptible in this situation as those countries are densely populated countries. As of 20 July 2020, according to the Institute of Epidemiology, Disease Control Research (IEDCR,2020), there are 207,453 confirmed COVID-19 cases in Bangladesh, including 2,668 related deaths, case Fatality Rate (CFR) 1.29%.and this transmission is higher in Dhaka city comparing to the other divisions of Bangladesh. Urban dwellers are highly vulnerable at that stage especially those whom are urban poor. Today, 4 billion people around the world more than half the global population live in urban areas.(World Bank Group,2020)

In Bangladesh, COVID-19 pandemic has already brought miseries to the people where concern keeps growing over whether an epidemic can be kept at bay. One of the most, if not the most at-risk groups are thought to be capital Dhaka's homeless and slum-dwellers, the urban poor. Known as the ninth-largest and sixth-most densely populated city in the world with a population estimated by the UN at over 21 million (the last census held in 2011 put it at 9 million), Dhaka is dealing with its 3,394 overcrowded slums where people have almost zero knowledge about the contagious virus and ways of protection to keep themselves safe from the impact of this new hazard. A majority of these poor people have been living in the urban slums or places such as the bus-rail stations for years in the city. (HOSSAIN,MD.I,2020) About 16.5 million people may slip below the poverty line in the country due to the ongoing Covid-19 epidemic. (Paramo, C.S, 2020), Even Majority of dwellers has no knowledge about deadly diseases. Especially, slum-dwellers are suffering from water supply, lack of accessibility of soap and detergents within pandemic situation, brought their life highly vulnerable and marginalized. In general, there is a lack of studies regarding awareness and attitude of the urban poor towards infectious diseases. That is the most crucial focusing arena of the study for exploring the level of knowledge and awareness among urban poor.

Objectives:

- To examine the socio-demographic background of urban poor.
- To explore the level of knowledge among urban poor regarding COVID-19
- To investigate the Awareness regarding risk-factors associated with COVID-19

Background of the Study

Due to erratic growth of COVID-19 across the globe, World Health Organization (WHO In 2019, a newly discovered infectious disease known as a coronavirus (COVID-19) was first identified in Wuhan, China in December.) considered it as a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) on 30 Jan 2020 After verifying the outbreak at perturbing levels of spread and severity, on March 11, WHO characterized COVID-19 as a pandemic (Sachina Paudel Prabin Shrestha Isha Karmacharya , Om Krishna Pathak, 2020). At a time, it spread all over the world. Social Physical distancing, wearing mask hand-gloves, face-masks, those are the most important preventive measures to prevent the spread of the pandemic.

When I were conducting my research, saw a women in front of me going outside for working purposes, Selina Begum, age-31, dweller of slum, she did not wear any face mask, I asked her why she did this, She answered me that, "As they are poor, only Allah will protect them from this pandemic, this is the curse by Allah and masks, hand gloves, social distancing those are only matter of self-satisfaction". She almost denied the risk-factors associated with COVID-19. That was the opinion of Selina Begun, there are so many Selina still exists in slum, still they are not aware of its deadly outcomes, it was just a portrayed of a single slum within Dhaka city, while conducting my research, I explored some existing perceptions among slum dwellers, Those are: social stigma, superstitious belief among slum dwellers, high expenses of safety products: Mask, hand sanitizers, gloves, avoiding social and physical distancing, sneezing and coughing everywhere without having protection, No local NGO's contribution, lack of Government support.

Place: Kamranghicha Slum, June, 2020, Dhaka City, Bangladesh

COVID-19: In the context of south Asia and Bangladesh:

The impacts of the health and economic crises linked to the COVID-19 pandemic are far from uniform along the income distribution of the populations in South Asia. Poorer households usually suffer from multiple deprivations and tend to have worse initial health conditions and less access to health services and care. These factors can make the health consequences of the pandemic more severe for people toward the bottom of the distribution. An important reason for this gradient of morbidity-related deaths is that poor people have lower access to health services or even to simple water and soap. People have lower access to health services or even to simple water and soap. In Nepal and Afghanistan, for example, women in around 80 percent of the poorest households report that distance is a 'big' problem in using health services, while this is the case only for about 20 percent for the richest group in Nepal, and 40 percent in Afghanistan. (South-Asia Economic Focus Spring 2020, World Bank)

Place: Kamranghicha Slum, June, 2020, Dhaka City, Bangladesh

Similarly, In Bangladesh, people have lack of awareness regarding COVID-19, Majority of these slum dwellers live a life without basic amenities. Handwashing facilities are expected much less in slum settlements than in non-slum settlements.. 'Kuhini (40), stated that within this they have only one tube-well for thirty families. Hence, slum dwellers find it difficult to wash hands with soap and running water, lack of water supply, increases the possibilities of COVID-19 expansion. Overall, Lack of water supply, sanitation problem and expense of sanitizer and masks create inequality among urban poor. In the perspective of Bangladesh, some urban poor stated that "A bar of antiseptic soap is ranged between Tk 40-50 and a bottle of liquid hand-wash is over hundred Tk . that is too much for poor people like them, "Due to this factors, Majority of people of urban poor have lack of awareness and knowledge regarding COVID-19, Eventually, This is the frequent issue of every single slum not in Bangladesh but also in south Asian slums.

Literature Review

Farhana, KM & Mannan KM, 2020, In their study they explored the knowledge and perceptions of about COVID-19 in Bangladesh. This study is a cross sectional design with mixed method approach. They exclaimed that, a poor understanding of the disease among the general people and healthcare workers may implicate in delayed treatment and the rapid spread of infection. Appropriate statistical analysis was performed as the Chi-square test was used to investigate the level of association among variables. A total of 435 completed the study questionnaire, Findings shows that in total study, (71.26.6%) was men and (28.73%) was women, and most of them are age range 41-50 years of age (80.45%). Respondents are doctors (31.18%), medical students (29.88%), public service (7.35%) and from other professions (30.57%). All of the participants agreed that they heard about COVID-19 (97.8%). Most of them used social media to obtain regarding the COVID-19 information. The findings of this study suggest significant knowledge gaps between the amount of information available about COVID-19 and the depth of knowledge among the healthcare personnel and general people. As the global threat of COVID-19 continues to emerge, it is critical to improving knowledge and perceptions among the general people and healthcare professionals in Bangladesh.

Islam T, , Kibria, M,B, 2020: In their study “ Challenges to the prevention of COVID-19 spread in slums of Bangladesh” they tried to investigate about recent hygiene condition of slums regarding pandemic situation. As he stated that, more than one-third of the population lives in urban areas in Bangladesh. Of the total urban population, 55% live in slums. The aim of the study is to explore the health-seeking behavior and preventive measures regarding COVID-19 among urban poor people He exclaimed that, in Bangladesh slum dwellers facing challenges such as congestion, inadequate water supply, poor sanitation facilities, poverty and lack of awareness of COVID-19. Slum dwellers are poor and engaged in daily wage-based occupations. So, they have to go out every day for their livelihood even during lockdown. Findings of the study outlined, physical distancing, keeping at least 3 feet away from the nearest person while coughing, sneezing and even speaking, is an important measure to prevent the spread of the pandemic within slum. Moreover, he suggested minimizing the spread of COVID-19, some effective measures should be taken for slum dwellers. Temporary shelters, including living space, handwashing facilities and latrines

should be built to meet their additional housing needs during the virus pandemic

Paude, S, Shrestha P; Karmacharya, I, Pathak,O,K 2020, The objective of this study was to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of COVID-19 among Nepalese population, as containment of the disease is only possible with the change in behaviors as preventive measures. It was web-based cross-sectional survey that conducted for a period of two month among Nepalese residents aged ≥ 18 years using a previously validated tool. Unrestricted self-selected, convenient sampling method was adopted to generate a heterogeneous sample. Data were analyzed in SPSS version 22 using chi-square/Fisher-exact test, independent t-test, multiple linear regression and binary logistic regression. Results out of 766 participants, 78.3% were aged 20–39 years and 58.2% were residents of province 3. One-third of the respondents were students followed by health workers. The rates for correct answer for COVID-19 knowledge questionnaire ranged from 30–99% with health workers and participants with bachelor's degree having significantly better knowledge. Of the total participants, 71.5% agreed that COVID-19 will be effectively controlled and 80% were assured that Nepal could win against COVID-19. The majority of the participants had not visited any crowded place (93.1%) which was significantly associated with age, marital status, gender, education, occupation, province of residence, and knowledge score of COVID-19.

Labban L, Thallaj N and Labban, A,2020: The aim of the study is to investigates the level of awareness about COVID 19. The aim of the research is to assess the current level of awareness towards COVID 19 among Syrians through a well-designed questionnaire. This study was conducted through a valid and reliable questionnaire including socio-demographic and COVID 19 knowledge data. Data were collected online from a sample of 400 respondents. The main objectives of this study were to study the awareness of Syrian people about the knowledge of information about COVID 19 and protection methods. The major findings of this study are that mostly people do have not awareness about COVID 19, transmission and prevention methods. The majority of the participants showed generally moderate knowledge about COVID 19. Age, education, level of education and occupation were the only significant factors that improved the level awareness. Groups of respondents of age 35-50 years, college graduates, medical professions and income over than 300,000 Syrian Pounds showed high level of knowledge and awareness of COVID 19 whereas low income and low education level respondents

showed the opposite. Empowering public information regarding the epidemiology of the COVID 19 is needed. Medical profession respondents can be helpful in educating other groups and they can communicate with health care providers in order to control COVID 19 outbreak.

Abdelhafz AS; Mohammed Z; Ibrahim ME Ziady H · Alorabi H, Ayyad M, Sultan E.A, 2020. The goal of this study is to assess the knowledge, perceptions and attitude of the Egyptian public towards the COVID-19 disease. a cross-sectional survey was conducted about these points, which was distributed among adult Egyptians. Five hundred and fifty nine persons completed the survey. Findings of the study explored that, the mean knowledge score was 16.39 out of 23, gained mainly through social media (66.9%), and the internet (58.3%). Knowledge was significantly lower among older, less educated, lower income participants, and rural residents. One of the most important finding is, almost participants (86.9%) were concerned about the risk of infection. About 73.0% were looking forward to get the vaccine when available. In general, participants had a good knowledge about the disease and a positive attitude towards protective measures. This knowledge is gained mainly through novel media channels, which have pros and cons.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted in urban slum during the period from July, 2020 to July 30, 2020. Structured interview schedule conducted on urban slum regarding knowledge and awareness of COVID-19. The study was carried out in Kamrangichar slum of Dhaka city. It takes one week to cover the whole areas, as the situation is much sensitive. The formula size of my study is determined using the formula given by Cochran Formula for the calculation of smaller population. 269 respondents (both male and female) were selected from this slum. Due to lack of time and budgeting 70% respondents were selected for this study. A convenience sampling technique was conducted in this study.

In this Study, Independent variables were included in the study, namely, gender, age of the respondents, education, working status, religion, education etc. here gender was categorized as male and female, Age also categorized as follows: below-18, 18-30, above-30. Respondent's education is the most crucial factors that stratified as: Illiteracy, can sign, primary, secondary education and others in the context of Bangladesh, respondents' current working status is also most influencing aspect regarding knowledge of COVID-19. A set of

dependent variables were included in the study, namely, knowledge and awareness of COVID-19, gender based awareness, loss of jobs, access to mass media, Involvement with NGO program, location of NGOs near at house, role of Govt. and risk factors associated with COVID-19, knowledges about its prevention, knowledges regarding social distancing, quarantine, wearing masks and gloves among slum dwellers. Both relevant primary and secondary data has used in this research. For investigating significant association between variables and analysis knowledge regarding among slum dwellers, frequency, chi-square and multinomial logistic regression has performed. SPSS (windows version 21) had been preferred for statistical analysis of this small scale data.

Result and Analysis

This study had been conducted within urban slum of Dhaka City, this study tried to explore association among socio-demographic factors and knowledge level of slum dwellers regarding COVID-19, this virus are quite frequent word among slum dwellers, they heard about it, but still they have lack of knowledge regarding quarantine, social distance and its prevention. According to the survey, 67.3% respondents heard about COVID-19 and they are quite knowledgeable about it, and almost 19.7 have blur knowledge about it. 13.0% defined they have no knowledge about it. Some exclaimed they did not hear about this name. The association between level of knowledge and independent variables are compiled it in Table 1, shows that, the knowledge level about COVID-19 among slum dwellers comparatively, higher within male respondent group (67.6%) rather than female respondents (66.9%).

Among female respondents, 20.3% have never heard about that disease, and 12.8% have lack knowledge about it. Whereas, 19.1% respondents have never heard about this contagious disease and rest of them have lack of knowledge about it. Table-1 also focused on age-group, where, explore that, age-group < 30 has higher awareness level of knowledge (51.7%) compare to others. Age-group 18-30 denotes 29% and > 18 denotes 19% level of knowledge among slum dwellers. According gender perspective male respondents have higher level of knowledge (51.7%) compare to female respondents (50.6%). This survey explored that comparatively employed respondents have 56.1% higher level of knowledge than 43.9% unemployed respondents.

Table: 1, the result of chi-Square test regarding level of awareness of COVID-19 among slum dweller.

Socio-demographic factors	levels	% level of knowledge regarding COVID-19				P Value
		Yes	No	Don't Know	Total	
Age	Below-18	55.8%	19.2%	25.0%	52 (19.3%)	4.893 ^a
	18-30	71.8%	12.8%	15.4%	78 (29%)	
	Above-30	69.1%	10.8%	20.1%	139(51.7%)	
Gender	Male	67.6%	13.2%	19.1%	136 (50.6%)	0.064 ^a
	Female	66.9%	12.8%	20.3%	133 (49.4)	
Respondents working Status	Employed	81.3%	7.1%	11.6%	155 (56.1%)	32.641 ^a
	Unemployed	48.2%	21.1%	30.7%	114 (43.9%)	
Religion	Islam	71.3%	12.2%	16.5%	237 (88.1%)	26.463 ^a
	Hinduism	33.3%	14.8%	51.9%	27 (10.0%)	
	Christianity	100%	0.0%	0.0%	1 (0.4%)	
	others	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%	4 (1.5%)	
Education	Illiterate	35.3%	14.7%	50.0%	34 (12.6%)	31.627 ^a
	Can sign	63.5%	18.8%	17.7%	96 (35.7%)	
	Primary Edu	76.0%	9.4%	14.6%	96 (35.7%)	
	Higher Sec. Edu	84.0%	4.0%	12.0%	25 (9.3%)	
	others	77.8%	11.1%	11.1%	18 (6.7%)	

Note: P value <000.1

In this study, education of respondents represents high significant association. This survey assesses that highest level of knowledge 84.0% found within higher-secondary category followed by 70% has found within primary education category. Other categories showed low level of knowledge regarding COVID-19. Religion is one of most crucial component and socio-demographic factors. As majority of the respondents are belongs to Muslim community, this category showed high level of knowledge 71.3% than other categories regarding COVID-19.

This study also explored most important indicators associated with COVID-19 among slum dwellers such as: knowledge level of its transmission, knowledge regarding of “social distancing” and “quarantine”, expense issue related with wearing mask and hand gloves, government support and loss of income.

Table: 2 Knowledge regarding influencing factors associated with COVID-19 among slum Dweller in Dhaka City

	% Knowledge regarding influencing factors associated with COVID-19 of slum Dweller		
	Yes	No	Don't Know
COVID is a contagious Disease	49.1%	23.4%	27.5%
Transmission through sneeze and cough	61.0%	10.0%	29.0%
Knowledge regarding Social Distancing	34.2%	42.0%	23.8%
Knowledge regarding Quarantine	38.7%	39.8%	21.6%
Expense of Masks according to income	87.7%	1.9%	10.4%
Loss of income sources	69.9%	21.9%	8.2%
It can be cured by proper nutritious food	42.8%	10.8%	46.5%
Receiving emergency relief from GOVT	10.8%	86.6%	2.6%

Table 2, represents that, 49.1% have knowledge that “COVID is a contagious Disease”, rest of them, have lack of knowledge about it. It is the matter of great unfortunate that respondents have low level of knowledge about quarantine and social distancing. Tabe-1 shows that only 34.2% respondents have knowledge about social distancing and 38.7% respondents have heard about quarantine. Unfortunately rest of them did not hear about it. Some explained it negatively.

Table: 3, Sources being knowledgeable about COVID-19

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Television	75	27.9	27.9	27.9
Friends and Relatives	54	20.1	20.1	48.0
Local Announcement	94	34.9	34.9	82.9
Social Media	18	6.7	6.7	89.6
Radio	4	1.5	1.5	91.1
others	24	8.9	8.9	100.0
Total	269	100.0	100.0	

Majority almost 87.7% respondents claimed that they unable to afford masks and hand gloves, because those are quite expensive. As majority of respondents lost their job, it's quite tough for all of them to buy marks frequently. 61.0% have knowledgeable that COVID-19 has transmitted through sneeze and cough of affected person. Rest of them claimed they don't have knowledge about it. Some skipped that answer. Table:2, shows that, 69.9% respondents stated that they have already lost their income sources, majority were engaged with garment and informal sectors before pandemic situation. But now they are spending miserable life. 42.8% respondents have knowledge regarding its prevention. Majority claimed that they don't know how to prevent the COVID-19. Additionally, they stated that, NGO's, health organization and government have lack of Additionally, Table-3, shows that, almost 34.9% exclaimed that they heard about it from local announcement by Government. 27.9% aware of it through the Television announcement, additionally, 20.1% heard about COVID-19 from friends, relatives and neighbors. Social media, radio and others sources also played vital role to defuse the knowledge and awareness of COVID-19 among slum dwellers.

Table 4 , Multinomial logistic regression model predictions of Odds Ratios (ORs) and Confidence Intervals (CI) for association between socio-demographic factors and knowledge regarding COVID-19

Socio-demographic factors	levels	Have knowledge regarding COVID-19 "YES"	Not knowledge regarding COVID-19 "NO"
		Odds Ratio (95% CI)	Odds Ratio (95% CI)
Age	Below-18	1.025 (0.420-2.501)	0.949 (0.384-2.343)
	18-30	1.432 (0.588-3.487)	1.432 (0.588-3.487)
	Above-30	-----	-----
Gender	Male	1.000 (0.496-2.015)	0.949 (0.384-2.343)
	Female (RC)	-----	-----
Respondents working Status	Employed	3.538 (1.651-7.581)	3.538 (1.651-7.581)
	Unemployed	-----	-----
Education	Illiterate	0.077 (0.013-0.457)	0.324 (0.034-3.109)
	Can sign	0.484 (0.089-2.634)	1.152 (0.136-9.793)
	Primary Edu	0.771 (0.140-4.234)	0.760 (.084-6.839)
	Higher Sec. Edu	0.774 (0.098-6.084)	0.302 (0.014-6.571)
	others	-----	-----

Significance at $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.1$

For exploring associated confidence interval (95%) and odd ratio, multinomial logistic regression has been employed, Table 4, shows according to this model, Respondents education, working status and religion explored a statistically significant effect knowledge regarding COVID-19 among slum dwellers. Inverse, Age and gender lose statistically significance effects on knowledge regarding COVID-19. In this Analysis, Age is the most crucial factor, table -4 shows that, age below 18 has 0.949 times less knowledge regarding COVID-19 than Aged within (18-30) , comparatively female respondents has (OR=0.949) (95% CL=0.384-2.343) time less knowledge regarding COVID-19 than male respondents.

Education is the one of the most determining indicator. Respondents whose have received higher- secondary education has 0.774 times higher knowledge regarding COVID-19 than who had received primary and others education, additionally those are illiterate and can sign. Along with these, respondents' current working status also denotes a higher statistical association. Respondents whom are employed, they have (OR=3.538) (95% CL=1.651-7.581) times higher knowledge than unemployed respondents of this Dhaka slum.

Discussion and Conclusion

Moreover, South Asia entered the global pandemic with a number of pre-existing gaps in public health infrastructure and access to basic amenities such as sanitation and broadband connectivity, gender inequalities, pervasive informality, and inadequate social protection. For recovering this situation, community participation and whole-of government and whole-of-society approaches might be effective (COVID-19 and South Asia, UNESCAP, 2019), Whereas, In Bangladesh, situation is almost neutral. Government is providing support and assistance to the vulnerable groups. Unfortunately, in slums of city has found with extreme health inequality. Lack of awareness regarding COVID-19, potentially made the life of slum dwellers more vulnerable. If awareness level will not accelerate, within second wave of this pandemic, situation will occur much hazardous among poor and vulnerable people of Bangladesh. From this survey, positive result found in "Transmission through sneeze and cough", majority of the respondents of urban slums have knowledge that COVID-19 spread through sneeze and cough of infected people. Inverse, through this survey, majority explained their deficiency of knowledge regarding social distancing and quarantine.

After all, if this awareness level will not be accelerated among this group, it will become the consequences of high amount of live loss in the second wave of COVID-19 pandemic.

In the meantime, COVID-19 is not only making the poor poorer but creating a vast group of “new poor”, hopefully temporarily. Majority of respondents of this study stated that, they lost their job. Additionally rest of the respondents stated that, masks and germ killing instruments are very costly according to their income. People are relying on government assistance: Lockdown success and trust in government policies depend on clear information and immediate relief. Messages are most effective when reinforced independently by multiple sources. Relief should be distributed accountably, with wide social involvement shared across television, News outlets, radio and social media. Punitive measures will greatly demoralize people currently facing the greatest hardship, and are likely to prompt resistance, violating social distancing and lockdown rules. (Dhaka Tribune, Oct 01, 2020). Within COVID-19 pandemic situation, though urban poor experienced enormous challenges, in this survey, unfortunately, only 10% respondent stated that, they only received emergency relief from government, positive aspects also found among poor within Bangladesh: they have displayed great kindness and support to their neighbors, friends and family during lockdowns such as sharing food, distributing food assistance packages, and lending money. Local community leaders and members distributed relief among urban poor. Local NGO's and local health workers contributed highly for building awareness among urban poor. They also distributed soaps, masks and hand-made sanitizers among slum dwellers. Thus, those supportive measures helped the urban poor in Bangladesh to overcome this situation. Otherwise, majority urban poor would be lead highly vulnerable life.

Additionally for getting knowledge, respondents preferred local announcement more than radio television. But majority stated they did not get clear knowledge about it from announcement. Respondents need of clear knowledge about COVID-19 from health workers. Respondents stated not only knowledge they also want to know the prevention of this contagious disease. They also stated that government active participation can prevent spreading disease from urban slums of Bangladesh.

Policy to Be Needed

However, COVID-19 awareness must be defused within South Asian countries. Additionally Bangladesh is preparing to undertake a range of strategic measures to protect its vulnerable population from the COVID 19 and building awareness among urban poor.

- Awareness among the Urban poor on : how to prevent the Covid-19 how to protect family members from the transmission of Novel Corona Virus, the importance of social distancing, handwashing with soap home quarantine etc.
- Religious leaders and local leaders can raise the awareness to reach every community members, Awareness level can be raised through poster/leaflets, Television and social media are still working for raising awareness. Local health workers can be provided knowledge regarding COVID-19 and its prevention directly among slum dwellers.
- Nutritious and vitamin containing foods can prevent COVID-19, whereas, majority of urban poor has no knowledge about its prevention. It should be matter of great concern that those people whether effort to buy those foods or not. Special announcement should be mandatory regarding its prevention.
- Free masks accessibility knowledge and awareness raising campaigns should be raised by active citizen of the community. That's how community participation will be fruitful.
- The government should also introduce new social safety net strategies targeting vulnerable group, as majority of urban poor lost their jobs and became unemployed. Bangladesh government has already started providing assistance to the vulnerable groups to recover the situation.

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